

Wind speed vertical extrapolation model validation under uncertainty

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ABSTRACT

As the wind energy sector evolves, accurate predictions of complex, nonlinear phenomena are becoming increasingly crucial. While rigorous model validation frameworks are common in high-stakes disciplines like defense and safety, their adoption in wind energy has been limited. This manuscript addresses this gap by introducing a comprehensive validation framework tailored for wind energy systems. This framework integrates both aleatoric (natural variability) and epistemic (knowledge-based) uncertainties. This dual consideration allows for a more nuanced understanding of model performance, especially under varying experimental conditions. The validation framework is applied to a meteorological measurement dataset using a logarithmic vertical extrapolation model. We present a set of numerical tests that validation metrics should satisfy and compare several metrics, providing insights into the relative strengths and applicability.

1. Introduction

The design of turbine components and wind farms requires detailed predictions of the real world, which is complex and highly nonlinear. As scientific and computational power grows, it is becoming increasingly feasible to accurately model and predict complex phenomena related to wind energy systems, and there is now a plethora of computer models available to approximate true system dynamics, with a wide spectrum of computational cost and fidelity to real-world experiments. However, it is crucial to validate these models using physical experiments before relying on them when making important decisions. While it is generally accepted that nearly all engineering models are not completely reflective of the real-world due to mathematical simplifications, it is the engineers' job to decide which model to use, and in what conditions it will be reliable.

At the core of model validation is the goal of quantifying trust in the predictive capability of a model. While it is fairly common for engineers to quantify the agreement between wind energy model predictions and associated experiments, it is less common to predict what this implies about future experiments, and it is much more common to *qualify* agreement between experiments and models by plotting these quantities. As models are increasingly relied upon, validation should move away from a “thumbs up/thumbs down” mentality, where the agreement between predictions and a single experiment allows a model to be classified as valid for all future experiments, and towards the

rigorous validation frameworks developed for defense and safety applications [1–5], where model quality is predicted based on experimental conditions.

The concept of model validation is used somewhat loosely in the wind energy community, and often without reference to these mature frameworks. The agreement between computer models and reality can be qualified through visual inspection (the overwhelmingly popular decision) or quantified using validation metrics [6]. A new industry standard, IEC 61400 Wind energy generation systems Part 60: Validation of computational models is being developed and agreed upon by different members of the wind energy sector, and we hope to inform these discussions through the results and discussion in this study. We adopt the definition of model validation articulated by Ferson et al. [7]: quantification of the agreement between model and experiment and what this implies about future experiments.

As wind energy systems analysis heavily relies on computer models, several validation frameworks have been presented as part of various wind energy studies. Maniaci et al. [8], Maniaci and Naughton [9] present a detailed road map for validation of high-fidelity wind energy models. Veers et al. [10] recognize validation of high-fidelity models as one of the grand challenges in wind turbine systems. Madsen et al. [11] is an example of the typical model validation workflow in wind energy. The manuscript presents a validation of the Dynamic Wake Meandering model, which is one of the most widely-used models in

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wind farm flow modeling. This study does not take measurement or model uncertainty into account, and does not predict when the model will be more or less accurate in the future. This is representative of the typical model validation process in wind energy [12–14]. Coulling et al. [15] compared aeroelastic model predictions of a floating turbine to an experimental dataset, identifying accurate and lacking model aspects. While this does offer insights into when the model will be useful in future analysis, measurement and model uncertainties are not explicitly considered. Bodini and Optis [16] compared random forest, power-law, and log-law extrapolation models, highlighting the importance of careful design of model validation metrics and finding the power law to be the least accurate of the three models examined. Murcia Leon et al. [17] applied a formal validation framework to compare wind farm wake models to measurements and presented this validation framework with model form error estimation, explicitly considering model and measurement uncertainties. The work was extended in Murcia Leon [18], where model error is predicted as a function of the turbine spacing and wind farm depth.

In this study, we demonstrate a holistic framework for validating computer models for wind energy systems based on available experiments. Vertical wind speed extrapolation is one of the simplest models used in wind energy science, making it a useful demonstration case for the presented validation framework. The framework explicitly considers uncertainties arising from measurement error and limited temporal information, yielding a predictor of an anticipated validation metric in unseen environmental and experimental conditions.

The remainder of this manuscript is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the validation approach as well as the examined vertical extrapolation and uncertainty quantification methods. Section 3 presents the data and numerical approximation schemes used in this analysis. Section 4 discusses the validation model results. The conclusions of the study are presented in Section 5.

2. Methodology

The validation and model error predictor framework is presented in Section 2.1. This framework allows for an arbitrary validation metric to be used, provided that three rules with two corresponding tests are satisfied. We compare the characteristics of different validation metrics, which are defined in Section 2.2.

2.1. Validation framework

A validation campaign has the objective of quantifying model accuracy. The presented validation and error prediction framework manages uncertainty in the predictions and observations to construct a validation metric, which is a measure of model accuracy by estimating a distance between the observations and model predictions. Then, an error predictor is developed to predict the validation metric under new experimental conditions. The intended application is to be used as an indication of when experimental validation results can be confidently predicted without a validation experiment, in the context of model certification.

2.1.1. Aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty separation

Uncertainty can be broadly categorized as being aleatoric or epistemic [19–21]. Aleatoric uncertainty is variability that occurs naturally and cannot be reduced [22]. No matter how much effort we put into a campaign, we cannot reduce this source of uncertainty. For example, uncertainty due to temporal variability cannot be reduced without additional measurement time. Epistemic uncertainty is due to lack of knowledge. If a model or experimental procedure is improved, epistemic uncertainty is reduced [23]. In the presented validation framework, aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties are separated. Aleatoric uncertainties are used to develop cumulative density functions (CDFs) describing the observed outputs. Epistemic uncertainties are represented as different realizations of these CDFs.

When an experiment is performed, observed inputs, \mathbf{x} , and observed outputs, $\hat{f}(\mathbf{x})$, are available as time series, $\hat{f}(t)$ and $\mathbf{x}(t)$. This temporal variability is aleatoric, meaning that it cannot be reduced. There are measurement uncertainties in the observed inputs and outputs, which are considered epistemic uncertainties: if measurement instruments and setup are improved, then these uncertainty can be reduced. Finally, the errors in the model can be considered as model form uncertainties. Model uncertainty is epistemic uncertainty since improvements of the model can reduced them. For every single observation pair, i.e. for every time in the measurement campaign, one can express the true value of the output using the model evaluated at the true value of the inputs and the model form uncertainty; and as a function of the measurement outputs:

$$m(\mathbf{x} + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_x, \boldsymbol{\theta}) + \epsilon_m = \hat{f}(\mathbf{x}) + \epsilon_f \quad (1)$$

where $m(\hat{\mathbf{x}})$ is the model evaluated at the observed inputs, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_x$ is a realization of the measurement uncertainty in the inputs, $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is the model parameters, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_m$ is a realization of the model uncertainty and ϵ_f is a realization of the measurement uncertainty on the outputs. Note that the model uncertainty term, ϵ_m , is a complicated function that quantifies the model limitations.

For example, measurement uncertainties are often assumed to be normally distributed with zero mean and variance that depends on the observation,

$$\epsilon(f) \sim \frac{1}{\sigma(f)\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\epsilon}{\sigma(f)}\right)^2}, \quad (2)$$

where ϵ is a realization of the random variable, $\epsilon(f)$, and $\sigma(f)$ is the standard deviation of the sensor error. This quantity is meant to represent calibration uncertainty, operational uncertainty (e.g., boom and mast effects), and uncertainty arising from the data acquisition system.

In the specific application of this framework, the uncertainties in the measured and predicted velocities follow the same uncorrelated distribution, $\epsilon \sim \epsilon_x \sim \epsilon_f$. the true measured wind speed, $f(z, t)$, is approximated as a stochastic variable,

$$f(z_i, t_j)^{(k)} \approx \hat{f}(z_i, t_j) + \epsilon [\hat{f}(z_i, t_j)]^{(k)}, \quad (3)$$

where \hat{f} is the observed wind speed, $\epsilon^{(k)}$ is realization k of the random variable ϵ , and i, j , and k index height, time, and realizations of epistemic uncertainty.

The CDF operator is a convenient way to separate aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties. This is visualized in Fig. 1. The time series $m(x, t, \theta)$ and $f(x, t)$ are transformed to their CDFs, M and F , to separate aleatoric and epistemic uncertainties. Aleatoric uncertainty is captured by the CDF operator and epistemic uncertainty is represented as the variation in each CDF. The model error, ϵ_m , is implicitly captured by the resulting validation metric.

Given an inferred or observed $f(t)$ signal, the CDF can be computed with respect to temporal variability:

$$\text{CDF}[\{f(t) \forall t\}](x) = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T I[x, f(t)] dt \quad (4)$$

where

$$I(g, f) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } g < f \\ 1 & \text{if } g \geq f \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

is the Heaviside (“unit”) step function and T is the time elapsed.

We define the random function F as the CDF obtained when approximating $f(t)$ using Eq. (6),

$$F(g)^{(k)} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T I[g, \hat{f}(t) + \epsilon_f(t)^{(k)}] dt, \quad (6)$$

and we define the random function M (Eq. (7)) as the CDF obtained when approximating $f(t)$ using Eq. (6),

$$M(g)^{(k)} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T I[g, m[x(t) + \epsilon_x(t)^{(k)}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{(k)}]] dt. \quad (7)$$

Fig. 1. Example CDFs of a quantity of interest. The blue lines show the measured data. The orange lines show the model predictions given environmental measurements. The different lines reflect different Monte Carlo realizations of the epistemic sampling uncertainties.

The corresponding probability density distributions (PDFs) are defined as the derivatives of M and F with respect to g .

All validation metrics are measures of the distance between a model and reality. Our framework yields a distribution of metric values, reflecting a lack of knowledge of the true validation metric. This distribution corresponds to epistemic uncertainty. It may be useful to take a statistic of this distribution in practical applications of this validation framework. For example, the 90th percentile of a validation metric represents an unlikely case—i.e., where we expect the true validation metric to be less than this value 90 percent of the time. An alternative approach could be to take the mean value with respect to epistemic uncertainty which can perhaps be more easily understood.

The full proposed validation workflow is visualized in Fig. 2. The top row depicts the measurement process, where a validation database is curated. This includes uncertainty in the relevant measurements and calibration of the computational model parameters. In the bottom row, the validation database is used to estimate environmental conditions where the validation metric has not been observed. Each entry in the validation metric database is stochastic due to epistemic uncertainty. Separate Gaussian Process regressors are trained to predict each percentile of the observed validation metric distributions as a function of the environmental conditions. The final predictions are convolved to form a single predicted distribution.

2.1.2. Three rules and two tests

We propose that any mathematically sound wind energy system model validation workflow should respect the following three rules:

1. **Value in improved measurements:** A specific quantile of the validation metric should increase when the measurement uncertainties is larger.
2. **Value in increased measurement time:** A specific quantile of the validation metric should decrease when the measurement time is larger.
3. **Many measurements are not enough:** The value added by increased measurement time must be limited by model accuracy.

The first rule reflects a desire to have high-quality measurements. When increasing the quality and associated accuracy/precision of the model or instrumentation, the number that is ultimately used as a validation metric should be decreased. The second rule is a desire for more measurement time. When increasing the amount of observations, the validation metric should also decrease. This is balanced by the third

rule, which reflects that increasing measurement time should not drive the metric to zero in the absence of perfect model agreement. We have developed two numerical tests to assess different validation metrics within this context.

The first test artificially increases the measurement uncertainty,

$$\sigma(f) = \eta \sigma_0(f), \tag{8}$$

where $\sigma_0(f)$ is the specified epistemic uncertainty (i.e., Guide to the expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM) [24] type B uncertainties) of the measured quantity f , η is referred to as the uncertainty multiplier and is greater or equal to one, and $\sigma(f)$ is the epistemic measurement uncertainties assigned during the uncertainty test.

As previously discussed, the validation metric should generally grow when the uncertainty multiplier, η , is increased. If the validation metric decreases with an increasing uncertainty multiplier, this may create perverse incentives during validation campaigns, where larger measurement uncertainties yield campaign results with greater perceived value. When performing this test, we use the entire dataset to compute the evaluation metric for different values of η .

The second test examines convergence with respect to the number of time samples. Because our framework separates aleatory and epistemic uncertainties, it is necessary to first specify a desired statistic of the distribution of predicted validation metrics (e.g., the mean or 90th percentile). Then, the average behavior of this metric is recorded as a function of the number of observations. Several short windows in time are used to report this mean across time. It is necessary to use time windows that are short relative to the total time horizon to avoid converging the variability across time windows. It is required that this time-window-averaged validation metric decrease as the number of observations are increased. Without this stipulation, there is no incentive to reward longer observation periods.

These two tests correspond to the first two rules presented at the beginning of this section. It seems impractical to demand a numerical test corresponding to the third rule, as this would require arbitrarily increasing the available measured data. But some deficiencies can be identified by taking an analytic limit. For example, any metric that divides the validation metric that is ultimately used by the number of samples will converge to zero regardless of the model quality, violating the third rule.

Both of these tests are performed visually by making line plots. It would be a simple extension to automate these tests.

Fig. 2. Visualization of the proposed model validation framework. In the top figure, a measurement campaign is performed to obtain a validation metric. In the bottom figure, a database of validation metrics (left) is used to construct several Gaussian Process (GP) quantile regressors (right).

2.2. Validation metrics examined

The presented validation framework is used to compared to different candidate validation metrics using the tests described in Section 2.1.2. While we attempt to give a comprehensive suite of different validation metrics, the reality is that there are virtually infinite validation metrics that could be defined.

The framework anticipates epistemic uncertainty in the measured validation metric, and suggests quantile regression to manage this uncertainty. The epistemic uncertainty (i.e., GUM type B uncertainty) is measured using Monte Carlo simulations, where the $\cdot^{(k)}$ superscript denotes Monte Carlo evaluation k .

We define root-mean-squared-error (RMSE) and mean-absolute-error (MAE) metrics, to contrast to the CDF-based approaches previously discussed:

$$RMSE^{(k)} = \left(\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{t=1}^{N_t} [f^{(k)}(t) - m^{(k)}(t)]^2 \right)^{1/2} \quad (9)$$

and

$$MAE^{(k)} = \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{t=1}^{N_t} |f^{(k)}(t) - m^{(k)}(t)| \quad (10)$$

where N_t is the number of time samples.

Similarly, we define an absolute bias metric. The bias validation metric is defined as

$$bias^{(k)} = \left| \frac{1}{N_t} \sum_{t=1}^{N_t} [f^{(k)}(t) - m^{(k)}(t)] \right| \quad (11)$$

Note that this is similar to the MAE, but the mean and absolute operations are in opposite order. We apply the absolute operation because negative and positive biases do not seem meaningfully distinguishable with the goal of quantifying model validity.

While these metrics are widely used, there is potential value in examining more advanced validation metrics. As nearly all engineering methods rely of some sort of distribution of outcomes, it is sensible to target the distance between the predicted and observed distributions. This can be accomplished by integrating across the time samples via a PDF or CDF operation, as previously defined.

The Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence measures the distance between predicted PDFs [25]. It is defined as

$$KL^{(k)} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{dM^{(k)}}{df} \ln \left(\frac{dM^{(k)}/df}{dF^{(k)}/df} \right) df. \quad (12)$$

A very small value was added to each computed PDF to avoid numerical instability in cases with small sample sizes.

An “area” validation metric is defined as

$$Area^{(k)} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |M^k(f) - F^k(f)| df, \quad (13)$$

which represents the area between predicted and observed CDFs. This metric and similar forms have been used in several validation studies and frameworks [2,4–7].

2.2.1. Error prediction

After computing the validation metric at different heights, the distribution of the validation metric can be estimated at a previously unseen height. This corresponds to predicting how useful a simulation will be at previously unseen, un-validated conditions. This requires the interpolation and/or extrapolation of the epistemic distribution of validation metrics.

In the presented framework, this distribution is interpolated/extrapolated on a quantile basis, to avoid making any assumptions about the shape of the distribution, using individual Gaussian Processes (GP),

$$q_i \sim GP^{(i)}(z | \{\pi_i[d(z)] \forall z \in \mathbf{z}_{\text{obs}}\}), \quad (14)$$

where q_i is the modeled quantile i of the validation metric $d(z)$, π_i is a function that returns quantile i , $GP^{(i)}$ is the Gaussian process regressor associated with quantile i of the validation metric, \mathbf{z}_{obs} is a vector or matrix of the observed experimental conditions (from which the observations are to be extrapolated). In some contexts, this model of the validation metric is referred to as the model error predictor.

When training each Gaussian Process, the observed data are pre-processed by subtracting the maximum value from the observed outputs. This ensures that the Gaussian Process prior will return to the largest observed error when predicting unseen data. We note that an arbitrary large value could also be used instead of the maximum observed error—the important aspect is that the Gaussian Process predict large values in unseen prediction regions.

The distribution of validation metrics can be drawn by drawing equal sample sizes from each quantile regressor,

$$d(z) \sim \bigcup \left(q_i^{(k)} \forall i \in [0, 1, \dots, 100], k \in [1, 2, \dots, K] \right) \quad (15)$$

where K is the number of Monte Carlo realizations of the stochastic regression model and the cup is the union operator.

We used a leave-one-out [26] approach to test the predictive capability of the examined validation metric. In this case, the predictions are defined as

$$q_i \sim GP^{(i)}(z | \{\pi_i[d(z)] \forall z \in \mathbf{z}_{\text{obs}}/z_{\text{LOO}}\}), \quad (16)$$

where z_{LOO} is the observed experimental conditions that the model is blinded to.

3. Application

The presented validation framework and vertical extrapolation model is applied to a wind speed dataset and a suite of validation metrics are examined. The wind speed data is presented in Section 3.1. Section 3.2 describes the vertical extrapolation model examined in this study.

3.1. Wind speed measurements

We examined two years of data from the tallest meteorological mast at the Risø Østerild measurement site. The mast instrumentation is visualized in Fig. A.10 in the appendices. The data ranges from 2020-05-07 to 2022-10-24, where the wind speed was logged at 35hz and 10 min averages were recorded. The signals used in this analysis are visualized in Fig. 3. While this is a relatively small data set in the context of resource assessment, it is important to keep in mind that most experimental campaigns do not often have such a large amount of available data.

The observation errors are estimated based on the RisøP2546 A sensor specifications. The error curve specified for the cup anemometer is visualized in Fig. 4. This is based on the IEC 61400-12 standard and

manufacturer specifications. While the errors are categorized by source, it is not specified if they are correlated in time (manifesting in some sort of sensor bias) or uncorrelated in time.

The correlation of uncertainty in time is a feature that could be measured and reported, but it is difficult to express using the GUM. For example, sensor installation/calibration errors are likely fully correlated in time. However, these detailed expressions of uncertainty are beyond what is currently used in practice. Neglecting the temporal correlation of the uncertainty may lead to overconfidence in model predictions.

The Monte Carlo vertical extrapolation methods are completely driven by the time series of measurement errors. The resulting stochastic timeseries are visualized in Fig. 5. We draw 2,000 Monte Carlo realizations of measurement errors when computing each validation metric. We examine the wind speed at 140 m when comparing the different validation metrics with the time convergence test and the speed at 244 m when applying the uncertainty increase test.

3.2. Wind speed vertical extrapolation with uncertainty propagation

This study examines a simple *log-law* vertical extrapolation model as a means to demonstrate the presented validation framework. We limit our analysis to this grossly simple extrapolation, though we note that there are more sophisticated approaches available for vertical extrapolation based on it [27–30]; further, some systematic uncertainty quantification has been done for power-law shear-extrapolation [31] but not with a formal validation framework such as that presented herein.

The logarithmic wind profile assumes the form

$$u(z) = \frac{u_*}{\kappa} \left[\ln \left(\frac{z}{z_0} \right) \right], \quad (17)$$

where z_0 is the surface roughness length, u_* is the friction velocity, and κ is the Von Kármán constant. This can be simply seen as a linear relationship in $\ln(z)$,

$$u(z) = a \ln(z) + b. \quad (18)$$

The a and b coefficients can be determined using linear regression:

$$a, b = \underset{a,b}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{i=1}^N [a \ln(z_i) + b - u_i]^2, \quad (19)$$

where N is the number of observations.

If the wind was measured without uncertainty, this would in principle be a deterministic model. When there are quantified uncertainties in the wind speed measurements, this becomes a stochastic model. For ease of notation, we define a random velocity variable as

$$u'(z, t) \sim u(z, t) + \epsilon(t), \quad (20)$$

where $\epsilon(t)$ is the measurement error associated with the observed wind speeds. We assume ϵ follows a normal distribution, centered about zero, where the standard deviation, σ , depends on the measured wind speed. We limit the simulated velocities to be strictly greater than zero.

Using a common least-squares regression approach [32], we can obtain the slope and offset with a vectorized function. The resulting stochastic linear regression is

$$a^{(k)}(t_j) = \frac{N \sum_{i=1}^N [\ln(z_i) u^{(k)}(z_i, t_j)] - \sum_{i=1}^N [\ln(z_i)] \sum_{i=1}^N [u^{(k)}(z_i, t_j)]}{N \sum_{i=1}^N [\ln(z_i)^2] - \left[\sum_{i=1}^N \ln(z_i) \right]^2} \quad (21)$$

and

$$b^{(k)}(t_j) = \frac{1}{N} \left(\sum_{i=1}^N [u^{(k)}(z_i, t_j)] - a_{kj} \sum_{i=1}^N \ln[z_i] \right), \quad (22)$$

where x_{ij} is N is the number of observed height-velocity pairs, i represents the index of the observed height, and j represents the index

Fig. 3. The full measured wind speed dataset used in the analysis. Different line colors correspond to different measurement heights. Each data point represents a ten-minute measurement average taken by a cup anemometer at the Risø Østerild measurement site.

Fig. 4. Estimated epistemic measurement errors based on manufacturer information and internal estimates.

of observed time. Using (22), instead of typical industrial practice taking a standard background roughness from a land-use or roughness map, in effect characterizes the z_0 uncertainty implicitly, in contrast with doing roughness uncertainty analysis as in [33]; however, the latter can be used and propagated in lieu of (22). This logarithmic model is compared to a power law model, which is identical to the above formulation but models the logarithm of speed as being linearly proportional to the logarithm of height.

4. Results

We applied the presented validation framework to assess how the logarithmic vertical extrapolation model agreed with the examined meteorological measurements. In Section 4.1, the two tests introduced in Section 2.1.2 are applied to the examined validation metrics introduced in Section 2.2. The behavior of these metrics is examined by changing the number of observations and the magnitude of the measurement uncertainty. In Section 4.2, sensitivity metrics that pass the proposed tests are applied to compare the accuracy of the logarithmic and power vertical extrapolation models. In Section 4.3, the observed area validation metrics are used to interpolate/extrapolate the uncertainty in the examined models when predicting speed or power in different conditions. These interpolation models are tested using unseen data via a leave-one-out analysis.

4.1. Comparing validation metrics

Fig. 6 shows selected results of applying the tests to each considered validation metric. The full results are summarized in Table 1 and are all included in Appendix B. Each line represents a different subset of the data, representative of what an analyst might find in practice. The top row shows the behavior of the different metrics with respect to the number of observations. The bottom row shows trends in the different metrics as the uncertainty is artificially enlarged, given 500 observations. The x -axis represents a multiplier that was applied to the measurement uncertainty curve. As uncertainty is increased, the model is perceived as being worse when using the RMSE and area metrics. In contrast, increasing uncertainty actually leads to more or similar confidence in the model when using the KS metric.

As the sample size grows, the MAE and RMSE, on average, stay the about same or slightly grow as the sample size is increased. This is problematic from a model validation standpoint—we should become more confident in our model as the number of observations increases, provided that there is agreement between the model and experiment. Both metrics monotonically increase with increased measurement uncertainty. The mean bias and KL divergence metrics do not monotonically increase with increases in uncertainty. The KL divergence shows non-linear behavior when increasing measurement uncertainty. The mean absolute bias stays constant as uncertainty is increased. When taking the 90th percentile of the absolute bias, the ultimate validation metric monotonically increases with increasing uncertainty. The area metric passes both tests when examining the mean and 90th percentile.

Based on these results, we recommend the area metric or the 90th percentile of the absolute bias when applying this validation framework. While the area metric is more robust to the statistic examined, using the 90th percentile of the absolute bias is a sufficient approach and the computation is considerably simpler than the area metric.

4.2. Comparing different models

The logarithmic vertical extrapolation model is compared to the power law model by computing the bias and area metrics. The results are shown in Fig. 7. Overall, the observed bias and area validation metrics are extremely similar. The power law is generally less accurate than the logarithmic model for the site and extrapolation heights considered, which is consistent with the findings of Kelly [27] and Bodini and Optis [16]. Both models generally become less accurate as they extrapolate to larger heights, which is also expected.

Fig. 5. Example evaluations of the stochastic timeseries associated with the measurements and model predictions for a given height. A subset of the full timeseries is shown.

Fig. 6. Example results of applying the time convergence (top) and uncertainty increase (bottom) tests. The left column shows results associated with the mean of the bias with respect to epistemic uncertainty. The middle column shows results associated with taking the 90th percentile of the KL divergence with respect to epistemic uncertainty. The right results show the results associated with the mean of the area metric with respect to epistemic uncertainty.

Table 1

Summary of results when applying the tests developed in Section 2.2 to different validation metrics. The Mean and P90 sub-columns correspond to what statistic is taken with respect to epistemic uncertainty in the computed validation metric.

Test	MAE		RMSE		Absolute Bias		KL Divergence		Area Metric	
	Mean	P90	Mean	P90	Mean	P90	Mean	P90	Mean	P90
Uncertainty	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓
Time	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

4.3. Model error prediction

The validation metric can be predicted at previously unseen locations after different validation experiments are conducted, and the mean absolute bias and area metric are computed for each experiment.

These predictions can inform engineers and analysts about how trustworthy the model will be in a new experiment. We used the observed distributions of validation metrics to create a probabilistic regression model. This regressor should reflect the prior beliefs of the practitioner. In our case, we pre-process the data so that the maximum observed

Fig. 7. Model comparison results using the area and bias validation metrics. The left plot is associated with the power law vertical extrapolation model and the right plot is associated with the log law vertical extrapolation model.

Fig. 8. Visualization of the model error predictor.

Fig. 9. Absolute bias (left) and area (right) validation metrics plotted as a function of direction and height. The top row is associated with validation of the log law and the bottom row is associated with the validation of the power law. The multicolored lines show different percentiles of the observed validation metric. The filled areas show the upper and lower bounds of different percentiles of the validation metric estimated, blinding the predictor to data associated with the examined height.

value is zero. This ensures that the Gaussian Process will yield large predictions in unseen regions.

The regression model was used to predict the two validation metrics at unseen heights, using the leave-one-out procedure described in Section 2.2.1. The results are shown in Fig. 8. Each column shows the observed and predicted validation metric, where the model has been blinded to the LOO height. The predictions fully envelop the observations, confirming that our error predictor is conservative. The absolute bias and area validation metrics are quite similar. In practice, the distribution of predicted validation metrics should be truncated above zero.

The measurement data used in this study is usually used in the context of measuring power curves, where the data must be carefully filtered to ensure high-quality wind and turbine measurement data. The anemometers used to record these data are mounted on a measurement mast (as shown in Appendix A), where the boom is orientated to the North of the mast, which corresponds to 0° in the measurement coordinate system. When the wind comes from the South (180°), the anemometers are waked by the mast mounting them, and we can expect the examined vertical extrapolation models to perform relatively poorly. The bias and area metrics associated with wind speed measurement/prediction are plotted as functions of direction and height in Fig. 9, examining the behavior of the logarithmic boundary layer model. For each height, data is withheld and the validation model is challenged to predict the recorded validation metric. The validation model generally is able to accurately interpolate between height measurements. The trends revealed by the bias and area validation metrics are nearly identical. These results are in agreement with the power curve testing procedures at the Risø Østerild measurement site, where wind speed data is often filtered to only consider inflow between 235° and 315° , where flow distortion from upstream obstructions is as low as possible.

5. Conclusions

This study presents a comprehensive framework for model validation and model form error prediction. The framework in this study was selected because it is well suited for wind energy applications. Measurements with larger uncertainty are naturally penalized, as opposed to approaches that purely reward overlap in the measured and predicted values. While the framework was applied to a simple case, this framework is appropriate in general for quantifying when an experiment is necessary. The extrapolation height (or more appropriately ratio of prediction to measurement height [31,34]) can be thought of as a stand-in or proxy for more complex variables, such as the wind farm characteristics when validating power models, the turbine characteristics when validating turbine models, etc. The percentile regression method is designed to be data-driven and conservative. As more samples are added, the Gaussian Process regressions are tuned to capture trends in the observations, providing a mathematically sound spread of reasonable uncertainty prediction of for a given percentile (P_{XX}).

The presented framework was developed with the mentality of quantifying the conditions under which a model will be reliable for future predictions. We hope that the presented findings and issued guidelines will better inform the development of the IEC 61400-60 standard. This requires the specification of threshold parameters which can be related to real-world metrics, such as uncertainty in the predicted AEP of a wind turbine. Determining these thresholds is a process that is highly specific to the individual or organization performing the model validation [35]. In reality, not all elements of the changes in experiments can be captured by the measurements, and analysts make a crucial assumption when deciding which model inputs to include in this framework.

In other works, validation metrics are sometimes used to add a spread or bias term(s) to the model predictions, adding probabilistic

bounds to the predicted outputs [36]. This represents the model-form uncertainty. For example, ϵ_m can be predicted as a function of time. We ultimately view the problem of model-form uncertainty quantification as fundamentally de-coupled from the problem of determining model validity. There are many approaches in the literature for dealing with model-form uncertainty, so we have conducted our analysis with the mentality of quantifying the degree of model trustworthiness, given a set of previous experiments.

In future work, we plan to apply the presented validation framework to more complex wind energy problems. First steps include slightly more complicated vertical extrapolation methods involving extended log-law forms (e.g., [34]) and shear-extrapolation [31]. As an example of yet more complex practical problems in wind energy, this framework can be used to predict which wake model will be most accurate in different wind farm configurations and atmospheric conditions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Julian Quick: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Juan Pablo Murcia Leon:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Carsten Weber Kock:** Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Valentino Servizi:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Nikolaj Stokholm Overgaard:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Nikolay Dimitrov:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mark Kelly:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Pierre-Elouan Réthoré:** Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Taeseong Kim:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Measurement instrumentation setup

The measurement mast used in this study is shown in Fig. A.10.

Appendix B. Full validation metric comparison

This appendix contains the full results of applying both tests to each of the examined validation metrics. In each figure, the first and third plots on the left show the results associated with taking the mean with respect to epistemic uncertainties, while the second and fourth plots rows are associated with the 90th percentile. Figs. B.11, B.12, B.13, B.14, and B.15 show the results of the two tests applied to the MAE, RMSE, absolute bias, KL-divergence, and area validation metrics, respectively.

Fig. A.10. The instrumentation used to acquire the experimental results in this study.

Fig. B.11. Results of the time (first two plots) and uncertainty (last two plots) tests applied to the MAE validation metric. The first and third plots show results associated with the mean with respect to epistemic uncertainty and the second and fourth plots shows the results associated with the 90th percentile with respect to epistemic uncertainty.

Fig. B.12. Results of the time (first two plots) and uncertainty (last two plots) tests applied to the RMSE validation metric. The first and third plots show results associated with the mean with respect to epistemic uncertainty and the second and fourth plots shows the results associated with the 90th percentile with respect to epistemic uncertainty.

Fig. B.13. Results of the time (first two plots) and uncertainty (last two plots) tests applied to the absolute bias validation metric. The first and third plots show results associated with the mean with respect to epistemic uncertainty and the second and fourth plots shows the results associated with the 90th percentile with respect to epistemic uncertainty.

Fig. B.14. Results of the time (first two plots) and uncertainty (last two plots) tests applied to the KL-divergence validation metric. The first and third plots show results associated with the mean with respect to epistemic uncertainty and the second and fourth plots shows the results associated with the 90th percentile with respect to epistemic uncertainty.

Fig. B.15. Results of the time (first two plots) and uncertainty (last two plots) tests applied to the area validation metric. The first and third plots show results associated with the mean with respect to epistemic uncertainty and the second and fourth plots shows the results associated with the 90th percentile with respect to epistemic uncertainty.

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